

PROPERTIES OF PARTICLE REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOYS IN CORRELATION WITH DIFFERENT PARTICLE SHAPES

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SUMMARY: The magnesium alloy QE22 (2.5% Ag, 2.0% RE, 0.6% Zr) was used as matrix material for particle reinforced magnesium base composites. The alloy was reinforced by Al₂O₃ platelets applying the squeeze casting technique to fabricate the composite whereas QE22/SiC_p composites were produced by powder metallurgical methods. To determine the influence of a particle reinforcement unreinforced materials were obtained for comparison using both production routes. Investigations have been carried out into mechanical properties and the microstructure of both composites and unreinforced materials in the as prepared and T6-heat treated condition. Particle reinforcement leads to a distinct improvement in Young's moduli of the magnesium alloy. The improvement is highest for plate-like particles and lowest when rounded particles are used. Using the Tsai-Halpin model to calculate the Young's moduli results in an overestimation of stiffnesses of almost all the composites. Reinforcement reduces elongations to fracture but increases the strength properties of the alloy.

KEYWORDS: Magnesium base composites, particle reinforcement, Tsai-Halpin model, microstructure, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for new and lightweight materials has forced the importance of magnesium as a constructional material in recent years. The use of magnesium on the other hand is limited by the low stiffness, the low strength at elevated temperatures, low wear resistance and the high coefficient of thermal expansion. Up to a certain degree these properties may be improved by conventional alloying techniques. A more extensive enhancement of critical properties is realisable by means of a reinforcing phase like particles, short fibres or long fibres. Reinforcement of magnesium materials by particles has proved to be advantageous as the production processes enable isotropic composites to be produced economically. The reinforcing effect is less than in the case of a fibre reinforcement but it is possible to achieve a whole range on properties that can be varied by varying the parameters such as matrix alloy, particle shape, size as well as particle volume fraction. Powder metallurgical as well as casting methods can be used to produce particle reinforced magnesium alloys. Both processes enable the manufacturing of near net shaped parts. In the powder metallurgical route gas atomised powder is mixed with the particles and subsequently

consolidated by extrusion, powder forging, etc. to fully dense materials. In the case of casting methods squeeze casting has proved to be very effective. The reinforcing phase which has to be shaped into porous preforms is infiltrated by the magnesium base alloy under pressure. The volume fraction of the reinforcement is limited by the produceability and uninfiltrability of the preforms.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Fabrication of Composites and Material Testing

To reinforce the alloy QE22 by alumina platelets preforms containing 20 vol.% Al_2O_3 platelets were infiltrated by the alloy applying the direct squeeze casting process. A sketch of the tool for the 500 t- squeeze casting press used for composite fabrication is given in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Direct squeeze casting press [1]

Starting the squeeze cast process the particle preform is put onto the bottom plate of the mould and the molten alloy is poured over the preform. Then the upper ram is vertically moved downwards to close the mould and to squeeze the melt into the preform. The applied pressure is exerted in two stages of 50 MPa for 15 sec and 130 MPa for 90 sec to prevent the melt from spraying out of the gap between ram and die and to ensure a complete infiltration of the preform. Following the infiltration the melt solidificates rapidly due to the difference of temperature between the melt and the tool. A premature solidification is avoided by preheating the preform up to 1000°C and overheating the melt up to 800°C [1]. Figure 2 shows a SEM micrograph of the alumina particles. The particles are in mono-crystalline condition and hexagonal shaped with a diameter of 15 μm and a thickness of around 1 μm . Further details of physical and mechanical properties of the particles can be taken from table 1 and the nominal composition of alloy QE22 is given in table 2 [3].

Fig. 2: Al_2O_3 platelets

Table 1: Physical and mechanical properties of $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ platelets

	Young's modulus [GPa]	aspect ratio (l/d)	density [g/cm ³]
$\alpha-Al_2O_3$	450	15:1	3,96

Table 2: Chemical composition of magnesium alloy QE22 (wt%)

	Ag	Cu	Fe	Mg	Mn	RE	Si	Zr
QE22	2,5	0,01	0,003	rem.	0,03	2,0	0,01	0,6

The production of P/M QE22/SiC_p composites was carried out by hot extrusion after mixing and milling of matrix powder and particles. The matrix powder was obtained from gas atomisation and showed an average size of $d_{50} = 39\mu m$ [4].

Fig. 3: SiC particles

Table 3: Physical and mechanical properties of SiC particles

	Young`s modulus [GPa]	aspect ratio (l/d)	density [g/cm ³]
SiC	400	plate-like: 3:1, blocky: 2:1, rounded: 1:1	3,21

To maintain a powder/particle size ratio of about 5:1 as proposed by Schröder [2] SiC particles possessing a mean diameter of $d_{50} = 9\mu\text{m}$ were incorporated as reinforcements in a volume fraction of 20%. The shapes of the particles were different: plate-like, blocky shaped and rounded particles (fig. 3). The properties of SiC particles are given in table 3 [3]. The powder/particle blends received from mixing and milling were precompacted and encapsulated to make extrusion possible. These capsules were heated for 30 min. at a temperature of 400°C before extrusion, which was executed by a 400t extrusion press. The degree of deformation ϕ [$\phi = \ln(A_0/A)$] was selected between 2,8 and 3,0.

Materials produced by squeeze casting and extrusion were machined into specimen for tensile testing with a diameter of 5mm and a gauge length of 25mm and samples for metallographic investigations. Tensile tests were carried out using an INSTRON 1095 testing machine with a cross head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The force was recorded by tension control using an extensometer to evaluate exactly the Young`s modulus. Light microscope and SEM were applied for microstructural analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure of composites

Fig. 4: Micrograph of QE22/Al₂O₃ platelet composite

As can be seen from figure 4 the QE22/Al₂O₃ composite shows a homogenous distribution of the platelets after squeeze casting. In some cases the preforms cracked due to high stresses and deformation of the preforms and small unreinforced areas were generated in the composite materials. This may be attributed to destruction and delamination of particles.

A T6 heat treatment (525°C/6h solution heating, oil quenching, 205°C/8h ageing) resulted in a formation of different precipitations like Mg₁₂(Nd₂Ag) and (Mg, Ag)₁₂Nd in the matrix.

Fig. 5: Microstructure of a P/M QE22/SiCp (20 vol.%, rounded), extrusion direction

Regarding the QE22/SiC_p composites produced by powder metallurgy a uniform distribution was found for the blocky shaped and rounded particles whereas the plate-like particles have a tendency to agglomerate. The particles became aligned in lines parallel to the direction of extrusion (fig. 5).

Mechanical properties of composites

A particle reinforcement of magnesium alloys appears to be most suitable, if an improvement of the elastic modulus is required. However, to estimate the degree of improvement using the linear or inverse rule of mixture is insufficient in the case of a particle reinforcement. A further development of these models, applicable to short fibres and particles, is the Tsai-Halpin model [5], which takes the geometry of the reinforcement into account (eqns. 1, 2):

$$E_C = \frac{E_M(1 + 2SqV_P)}{1 - qV_P} \quad (1)$$

when

$$q = \frac{(E_P / E_M) - 1}{(E_P / E_M) + 2S} \quad (2)$$

E_C, E_M, E_P = Young`s moduli of the composite, matrix and particles
 V_P = Volume fraction of particles
 S = particle aspect ratio (l/d)

It is evident from figure 6 and 7 that the enhancement of stiffness is overestimated by applying the Tsai-Halpin model except the QE22/SiC_{p (rounded)} composite in the heat treated condition, which elastic modulus is slightly underestimated. The discrepancy between the measured and calculated moduli becomes smaller with decreasing aspect ratio. Delamination and damage of particles as well as pores unavoidably remaining in the extruded material are responsible for these differences. A T6 heat treatment increases the Young`s modulus of squeeze casted QE22 in the unreinforced and reinforced condition. An alteration of stiffness

of alloy QE22 (P/M) is dependent on the shape of SiC particles used as reinforcements. The Young's modulus is increased most by plate-like particles from 46 GPa for the unreinforced alloy up to 77 GPa. The smallest increase is obtained from rounded particles. The heat treatment lowers the Young's modulus of unreinforced QE22 and equalises the moduli of all the P/M composite materials.

Fig. 6: Young's modulus of squeeze casted QE22 and QE22/20 vol.% Al₂O₃(platelet) composite

Fig. 7: Young's modulus of P/M produced QE22 and QE22/20 vol.% SiC_p composites

Regarding the tensile properties of the squeeze casted materials investigated the strongest increase of the ultimate tensile strength was obtained from the unreinforced alloy after heat treatment (fig. 8). However, the strengths of the composites are just below that value;

therefore a positive influence of the particle reinforcement on the tensile strength of squeeze casted QE22 is obvious. A more distinct improvement of tensile properties was achieved in the case of the powder metallurgically produced composites, as given in figure 9. Since the shape of blocky and rounded SiC particles is nearly globular they enhance the tensile strength more than plate-like particles do. A heat treatment hardly changes the different tensile strengths.

Fig. 8: Ultimate tensile strength of squeeze casted QE22 and QE22/Al₂O_{3(platelet)} composite

Fig. 9: Ultimate tensile strength of P/M produced QE22 and QE22/SiC_p composites

The particle reinforcement generally leads to a marked loss of ductility, which is seen from fig. 10 and 11. The elongation to fracture of the squeeze casted alloy decreases of about 90% due to the alumina platelets in the as cast and heat treated condition. The reduction of ductility of the P/M material depends as strength properties on the shape of SiC particles incorporated into the alloy. The composite reinforced by plate-like particles shows the lowest elongation to fracture of around 5%. With decreasing aspect ratio of the particles the ductility increases up to about 8% in the case of the rounded particles. The heat treatment reduces all the ductilities of the unreinforced alloy and composites.

Fig. 10: Elongation to fracture of squeeze casted QE22 and QE22/Al₂O₃(platelet) composite

Fig. 11: Elongation to fracture of P/M produced QE22 and QE22/SiC_p composites

CONCLUSIONS

Particle reinforced magnesium matrix composites can be produced using powder metallurgical methods as well as the squeeze casting technique. Various matrix alloys and particles of different shapes, sizes and volume fractions enable a manufacture of composites providing certain properties. The alloy investigated showed a distinct improvement of stiffness as a result of the particle reinforcement, which is independent of the production method applied. Using the Tsai-Halpin model to estimate elastic moduli of particle reinforced magnesium base composites seems to be suitable only for a small particle aspect ratio and composites free of microstructural defects. The tensile strength of alloy QE22 was increased by the alumina platelets incorporated by squeeze casting and the differently shaped SiC particles used for P/M techniques. In contrast to elastic moduli the strongest increase in strength was obtained by rounded particles. A condition for obtaining this improvement is a homogenous distribution of the particles throughout the matrix. Concerning the powder metallurgy this was achieved by maintaining a size ratio of matrix powder to particle of 5:1. However, all the composite materials showed a much lower elongation to fracture than the unreinforced alloys and this reduction of ductility varies with the shapes of particles. Reinforcements with globular particles appear to be appropriate for applications requiring high strengths combined with a sufficient ductility. Particles with a high aspect ratio such as plate-like particles should be used if a high stiffness is demanded.

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